

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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DEVELOPMENT OF AN ALGORITHM TO PREVENT HOSPITAL-ACQUIRED
PRESSURE INJURIES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Hospital-acquired pressure injuries (HAPIs) affect millions of patients yearly and have a tremendous impact on patients' quality of life and healthcare costs. The evidence suggests that HAPIs increase patients' pain, infection risk, morbidity, and mortality. Critically ill patients are at greater risk for developing HAPIs due to hemodynamic instability and vasoactive drug use. Prevention of HAPIs has been one of the biggest challenges in the healthcare industry due to the increased healthcare costs and its impact on patients' quality of life. Limited knowledge of nurses about current evidence-based practices to prevent HAPIs is a common problem in clinical settings. Aim: 1) To evaluate nurses' views of HAPI prevention practices, 2) To decrease the incidence of HAPIs for critically ill adults in an 8-bed ICU by 10% over one month by developing an algorithm for HAPI prevention and providing education to the nurses. Method: Using the PARIHS framework, this doctoral project examines the effects of a HAPI prevention algorithm tool on nursing views on pressure injury prevention. The project was piloted in an 8-bed intensive care unit of a 401-bed acute care hospital in Los Angeles, California. Participants were educated with the HAPI prevention algorithm. Anonymous pre-and post-intervention Likert scale surveys were provided to participants via Qualtrics. Results: Participants' overall responses resulted in an improved understanding of HAPI prevention and interventions. Several survey results demonstrated statistical significance. All responses showed clinical significance in HAPI prevention. Utilizing the evidence-based HAPI prevention algorithm tool revealed improved knowledge in preventing HAPIs, as evidenced by the decreased number of HAPIs in the pilot unit post-intervention.

Keywords: quality improvement, evidence-based practice, hospital-acquired pressure injuries, prevention, PARIHS framework, algorithm, intensive care unit

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Background

Hospital-acquired pressure injuries (HAPIs) affect approximately 2.5 million patients yearly (AHRQ, 2022). A HAPI results from localized damage to the skin or underlying soft tissue over a bony prominence (National Pressure Injury Advisory Panel [NPIAP], 2019). The injury occurs due to intense, prolonged pressure, and shear (NPIAP, 2019). Approximately 60,000 patients die due to HAPI each year (AHRQ, 2022). HAPIs have a tremendous impact on patients' quality of life, healthcare costs, and the healthcare provider's ability to render appropriate patient care (Rondinelli et al., 2018; Squitieri et al., 2018). HAPIs are responsible for up to \$11.6 billion in annual healthcare costs (Squitieri et al., 2018). HAPIs can interfere with the patient's full functional recovery and contribute to longer LOS (Squitieri et al., 2018). Furthermore, patients with HAPIs have a higher 30-day readmission rate of 22.6% versus 17.6% for non-HAPI-related hospitalizations (NPIAP, 2019).

HAPIs increase patients' pain, infection risk, morbidity, and mortality (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2022). HAPIs are identified as never events (Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services [CMS], 2023). According to the National Quality Forum (NQF), never events are errors in medical care that are preventable, identifiable, and have severe consequences for patients (CMS, 2023). More than 17,000 lawsuits have been related to HAPIs annually (AHRQ, 2022). It is the second most common lawsuit claim after a wrongful death (AHRQ, 2022). Prevention of HAPIs has been one of the biggest challenges in the healthcare industry (The Joint Commission [TJC], 2023).

Setting the Stage

Problem Statement

Analysis of baseline data at the project hospital located in Los Angeles County revealed that from January 2021 to December 2022, there were 485 HAPIs hospital-wide. Of the 485 HAPIs, 52% occurred in intensive care units (ICUs). Patients in the ICUs are at greater risk for the development of HAPIs due to hemodynamic instability, vasoactive drug use, and increased medical device use (CMS, 2023; Coyer et al., 2022; Tayyib et al., 2017). The project facility's quality and patient safety team, in collaboration with the hospital leadership, clinical nurse specialist (CNS), and wound care clinical nurse educator (WCCNE), acknowledged the problem in HAPI prevention and agreed to potential solutions to decrease the HAPI events in the hospital.

This project addresses the increased number of HAPIs in an acute care hospital in Los Angeles, California. Incidence uptake is occurring despite the reported use of evidence-based strategies to prevent the development of HAPIs. The nurses' views of HAPI prevention were assessed. An algorithm for HAPI prevention was developed as a tool for nurses.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to decrease the incidence of HAPIs for critically ill adults in an 8-bed ICU by 10% over one month by developing an algorithm for HAPI prevention and providing education to the nurses. This project evaluated nurses' views of HAPI prevention practices and developed a HAPI prevention algorithm tool (HAPI Prevention Algorithm in Appendix J).

Supporting Framework

As healthcare costs continue to rise globally, there is a drive to improve care using evidence-based interventions (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Roberts et al., 2021;

Rycroft-Malone, 2004; Ward et al., 2017). The EBP project was guided by the Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) framework (Figure 1). The PARIHS framework provided the foundation which assisted in the implementation and interpretation of the findings to determine the effectiveness of an intervention (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Roberts et al., 2021; Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

The PARIHS framework was developed in 1998 by Kitson et al. (2008) to address the need to evaluate the effectiveness of an intervention in healthcare settings. The PARIHS framework provides an equation that is applied to determine the successful implementation (SI) of an intervention which is a function (f) of the evidence (E) nature and type, context (C) quality, and the facilitation (F) of an outcome ($[SI = f(E, C, F)]$; Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Roberts et al., 2021; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). The PARIHS framework identified three core implementation constructs: facilitation, evidence, and context (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Roberts et al., 2021). The context and facilitation of an intervention to address a problem demonstrated the effective and successful implementation of the tools. Using the core elements, the DNP student integrated the PARIHS framework (Figure 2) into the project facility's HAPI prevention algorithm.

The first element of the PARIHS framework used evidence to guide the development of the interventions (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). The PARIHS framework identified evidence as research, clinical experience, local information (facility data), and culture (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). To be considered valued evidence-based research, the intervention should be well-designed, executed, and complemented by clinical experiences (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). At the project hospital, healthcare workers were accustomed to using

evidence-based guidelines to promote change. Staff viewed evidence as vital in accepting changes to their practices. Clinical experience and expertise were reflected upon and tested by individuals in relation to HAPI prevention. In addition, HAPI data and information related to them were collected, analyzed, and shared.

The second element of the PARIHS framework is the context in which the intervention was implemented, which can be a powerful mediator in implementing evidence into practice (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). In the PARIHS framework, context refers to the environment or setting where individuals receive their healthcare services (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Contextual factors served a vital role in facilitating research implementation. These factors were culture, leadership, and evaluation (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). A culture of decentralized decision-making between healthcare leaders and staff was conducive to facilitating change (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Decentralization of decision-making in healthcare providers participated in sharing opinions and ideas to improve healthcare services, creating a collaborative culture in the healthcare setting. The model promotes evaluation through feedback, resulting in a more refined process for change, since healthcare providers work together rather than in silos (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

The framework's second element is reflected in the project facility's ICU. It was conducive to the implementation of the HAPI prevention algorithm. The leader who was the project facilitator used transformational leadership to encourage staff to be empowered in the decision-making process. Transformational leaders inspire people to perform beyond their perceived abilities (Palanski et al., 2021). The facilitator collaborates with the unit practice

council (UPC) for shared governance. The UPC was an effective forum that can be used to facilitate nurse engagement. The UPC empowers nurses to make decisions about their practice and make changes that affect nursing care and patient outcomes (Kutney-Lee et al., 2020). The UPC provides a culture of patient-centeredness, innovation, and open communication. Furthermore, the evaluation method used pre-and -post-intervention staff surveys.

The third element of the PARIHS framework was facilitation, which was implementing an evidence-based practice change. In the PARIHS framework, high facilitation encompassed three broad themes: the facilitator's purpose, role, and skills (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Facilitation starts with providing support to healthcare providers. Facilitation then uses a specific task to finally use a holistic process to enable individuals to analyze, reflect, and change their practices (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). The skill of the facilitator is to adjust their role and style depending on the different phases of the intervention implemented, which helped to create lasting change (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004).

For this pilot project, the DNP candidate was the change facilitator. The facilitator had the appropriate skills, attributes, and knowledge about the project to implement the practice change. The facilitator's role was to help healthcare providers become reflective learners by helping them identify their learning needs, encourage them to be critical thinkers, guide process changes, and assess the achievement of their learning goals (Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Furthermore, the facilitator provided support and empowered individuals to promote change.

The PARIHS framework is a multidimensional model developed to epitomize the complexity of the change processes by implementing research-based clinical practices

(Bergstrom et al., 2020; Kitson et al., 2008; Roberts et al., 2021; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). This Doctorate in Nursing Practice (DNP) project used the PARIHS model to facilitate the adoption of a clinical algorithm to prevent HAPIs at the project facility.

Review of Literature

Overview

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to HAPI prevention. The review provided a rigorous and transparent method of summarizing the available research for this DNP project. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms utilized included, in various combinations with limiters: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, risk factors, nursing care plan, nursing, critical care, critical care unit, repositioning, positioning, early mobility, algorithm, and PARIHS framework.

Articles were included if they were published in English from 2017 to 2022. Two articles were selected, published in 1990 and 1994 as they pertained to the PARIHS framework and were considered seminal works. Articles were chosen despite their geographic origin if they were written English. Reference lists were reviewed for relevant articles and were included if they pertained to the project topic. Unpublished work, wound care-specific websites, and the AHRQ toolkit for hospital HAPI prevention were also selected. Twenty-three articles were identified utilizing comprehensive HAPI prevention programs. Additional articles, including critical care unit, algorithm, California Department of Public Health (CDPH), and HAPI care plans, were reviewed. This review of the literature was divided into the following sections: a) pathophysiology, b) risk factors, c) prevalence, d) nurse knowledge, e) nursing plan of care, f) algorithm integration, and g) PARIHS framework integration. Furthermore, an additional review of the literature was conducted on a) monitoring of progression, decline, and resolution of HAPI, b) maintenance of dressing changes, c) provider notification, d) pain relief strategies, e) wound

care team consult, f) nutritional consult, g) patient and family education, and h) nursing early mobility program.

Pathophysiology

Textbooks on pathophysiology were reviewed, and publications relevant to the pathophysiology of HAPIs were appraised using electronic databases in CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Key terms utilized included pathophysiology, HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, and decubitus ulcer. Reference lists of appraised articles and books were also searched for relevant articles.

The main factors contributing to pressure injuries were pressure, friction, shearing forces, and moisture (Mervis & Phillips, 2019; Morrison et al., 2022). Pressures exceeding normal capillary pressure result in decreased oxygenation and compromised circulation of the affected tissue (Mervis & Phillips, 2019; Morrison et al., 2022). If compression is not relieved, a pressure injury can develop in three to four hours, commonly occurring over the sacrum, ischial tuberosities, trochanters, malleoli, and heels (Mervis & Phillips, 2019; Morrison et al., 2022). Friction is the rubbing against cloth or bedding, which can trigger skin ulcerations by causing local erosion and breaks in the epidermis and superficial dermis (Mervis & Phillips, 2019; Morrison et al., 2022). Shearing combines downward pressure and friction, causing the skin to breakdown (Mervis & Phillips, 2019; Morrison et al., 2022). Furthermore, moisture, such as perspiration and incontinence, can lead to tissue breakdown and maceration, which worsen pressure injuries (Mervis & Phillips, 2019; Morrison et al., 2022).

Risk Factors

A search was conducted utilizing CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Search terms included HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, risk factors, critically ill,

mobility, activity, and perfusion. Critically ill patients are at the greatest risk for HAPI development (Coyer et al., 2022; Goodman et al., 2018; Pickham et al., 2018). Critically ill patients are more susceptible to risk factors for HAPI development as most critically ill patients are ventilated and sedated; thus, unable to care for themselves, move, or change position (Coyer et al., 2022; Tayyib et al., 2017).

The evidence identified three main factors contributing to HAPI development: reduced perfusion, immobility/inactivity, and critical illness (Coyer et al., 2022; Goodman et al., 2018). Reduced perfusion alterations include diabetes, vascular disease, poor circulation, blood pressure changes, smoking, and edema (Coyer et al., 2022; Tayyib et al., 2017). Limited mobility and activity resulting in lying or sitting on a specific part of the body render patients at greater risk of skin breakdown (Coyer et al., 2022; Tayyib et al., 2017). Furthermore, the patient's critical illness may involve hemodynamic instability and oxygenation disorders that can accelerate the effects of prolonged immobility (Coyer et al., 2022; Tayyib et al., 2017).

Prevalence

In this section of the literature review, a search was conducted utilizing CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Search terms included HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, HAPI prevalence, pressure injuries prevalence, pressure ulcer prevalence, and decubitus ulcer prevalence. Healthcare organizations strive to minimize harm and provide safe environments for patients. However, despite many prevention strategies, HAPIs continue to occur in critical care settings (Cox et al., 2022; Latimer et al., 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2019). HAPI prevalence is a healthcare quality marker (Cox et al., 2022; Latimer et al., 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2019). Rates of HAPIs have been reported to range from 2.8% to 53.4% in critical care units (Cox et al., 2022; Latimer et al., 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2019).

Nurse Knowledge

A literature review was conducted using CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, critical care nurse, nurse, intensive care unit, and critical care knowledge. Limits on the search included articles written between 2017 and 2022. Nursing knowledge of HAPI prevention varied. Some studies showed that nurses were highly knowledgeable in this area (Bakarat-Johnson et al., 2020; Fulbrook et al., 2019; Tirgari et al., 2018), while other researchers reported low levels of HAPI prevention knowledge (Alshahrani et al., 2021; Sala et al., 2021). Furthermore, some researchers reported a gap between nurses' knowledge and the use of evidence-based practices in HAPI prevention.

Some studies found that nurses had good knowledge and positive attitudes toward HAPI prevention interventions (Bakarat-Johnson et al., 2020; Fulbrook et al., 2019; Tirgari et al., 2018). However, other studies found that the application of preventative interventions to daily practice was lacking, often compounded by time constraints (Alshahrani et al., 2021; Sala et al., 2021). Some studies reported a lack of knowledge related to HAPI prevention, particularly in risk assessment, classification, and preventative strategies (Alshahrani et al., 2021; Sala et al., 2021). Limited nurse knowledge is a common healthcare problem where nurses are unaware of current care guidelines and evidence-based practices (Alshahrani et al., 2021; Dalvand et al., 2018; Sala et al., 2021). Some nurses' activities are not based on knowledge but intuition, habit, or experience (Alshahrani et al., 2021; Dalvand et al., 2018; Sala et al., 2021). Therefore, this can interfere with implementing HAPI prevention guidelines and algorithms.

Nursing Plan of Care

A literature review was conducted to gather research on the nursing plan of care related to HAPI prevention. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, nursing, care plan, and plan of care.

HAPI prevention plan of care translates the patient's risk assessment information into an action plan to address the individualized patient needs (Bakarat-Johnson et al., 2020; Fulbrook et al., 2019; Lovegrove et al., 2021). The nursing care plan synthesized individual patient data in a holistic approach to preventing HAPIs (Bakarat-Johnson et al., 2020; Fulbrook et al., 2019; Lovegrove et al., 2021). Optimal goals of HAPI care planning included healing of current pressure injuries, prevention of pressure injuries, maintenance of skin integrity, and achieving individual patient quality of life (Bakarat-Johnson et al., 2020; Fulbrook et al., 2019; Lovegrove et al., 2021).

The project's HAPI prevention algorithm included the facility's HAPI prevention nursing plan of care elements. The nursing plan of care consists of a) monitoring of HAPI progression, decline, and resolution; b) maintenance of dressing changes; c) updates to provider team regarding new HAPIs; d) application of HAPI pain relief strategies; e) wound care team consultation; f) nutritional consultation; g) patient/caregiver education on HAPI findings and treatment plan; and h) avoidance of positioning over tissue/skin injury. Furthermore, the project facilitator added the facility's nurse-led mobility program to the HAPI prevention algorithm.

Monitoring of Progression, Decline, and Resolution of HAPI

A literature review was conducted to gather research on monitoring HAPI progression, decline, and resolution. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google

Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms utilized included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, progression, decline, resolution, monitor, nursing, and nurse. The research demonstrated that healthcare providers should monitor progression, decline, and resolution of pressure injuries on an ongoing basis after admission to a healthcare facility (Lee et al., 2017; Niederauer et al., 2017; Short et al., 2022). Proactive assessment prevents the development of HAPIs, thus, reducing incidence rates (Lee et al., 2017; Niederauer et al., 2017; Short et al., 2022). Healthcare providers can help improve patient outcomes by preventing skin damage before it develops into a pressure injury (Lee et al., 2017; Niederauer et al., 2017; Short et al., 2022).

Maintenance of Dressing Changes

A literature review was conducted to gather research on maintenance of dressing changes related to HAPI prevention. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, dressing changes, pressure injury dressings, pressure ulcer dressings, and decubitus ulcer dressings. In addition, clinical trial registries and World Health Organization (WHO) International Clinical Trials Registry Platform were searched.

Evidence showed that the maintenance of dressing changes prevented the development of HAPIs (Aloweni et al., 2017; Forni et al., 2018; Walker et al., 2017). A study by Aloweni et al. (2017) presented statistically significant evidence that silicone foam dressing changes can prevent HAPIs. Similarly, the maintenance of multi-layer polyurethane foam dressing changes prevented the onset of HAPIs in critically ill patients (Hahnel et al., 2020; Walker et al., 2017).

Provider Notification

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to collaboration. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, provider notification, timely notification, notification, collaboration, provider, and physician. HAPI prevention included timely notification of pressure injury to the patient's healthcare provider (Armour et al., 2019; Black, 2019). The providers assessed various interventions available to facilitate healing of the HAPIs (Armour et al., 2019; Black, 2019). Furthermore, physicians documented the status of the pressure injury and documented the interventions for treatment and prevention of further injuries (Armour et al., 2019; Black, 2019).

Pain Relief Strategies

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to pain relief strategies on HAPIs. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, pain, pain relief, pain relief strategies, and strategies. Pain was a critical aspect of a pressure injury assessment (Scheffler et al., 2018; Yildirim et al., 2018). Localized pain identified areas where damage may be developing (Scheffler et al., 2018; Yildirim et al., 2018). To prevent adverse events, it was crucial to address the cause of pain, remove the external source, and apply nonpharmacological/pharmacological strategies for pain relief (Scheffler et al., 2018; Yildirim et al., 2018).

Wound Care Team Consult

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to wound care team consultation. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and

Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, wound care, wound care consult, consult, and consultation. Wound care specialty-trained nurses assisted in debridement of wounds, dressing changes, and continuous follow-up care (Lin et al., 2020; Walker et al., 2020). The wound care team also assisted in educating the patient and family (Lin et al., 2020; Walker et al., 2020). HAPIs can be very difficult to treat, so it is crucial that clinicians work together as an interprofessional team to provide the best care to monitor and prevent HAPIs (Lin et al., 2020; Walker et al., 2020).

Nutritional Consult

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to nutritionist or dietitian consults to prevent HAPIs. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, nutrition, nutritionist, and nutrition consult. Nutrition plays a significant role in skin and tissue preservation, viability, and pressure injury healing (Allingstrup et al., 2017; Munoz et al., 2020; Razzaghi et al., 2017). Nutritional consult is critical when patients are at risk of or have HAPIs (Allingstrup et al., 2017; Moore & Webster, 2018; Munoz et al., 2020; Razzaghi et al., 2017).

Early nutrition screening was key in identifying nutritional factors that can impede healing (Allingstrup et al., 2017; Munoz et al., 2020; Razzaghi et al., 2017). Strategies included early identification and management of malnutrition of patients at risk since it has been reported to improve health outcomes (Citty et al., 2019; Litchford et al., 2020; Moore & Webster, 2018). Timely identification and management of malnutrition are required to provide quality care for hospitalized patients (Citty et al., 2019; Litchford et al., 2020; Moore & Webster, 2018).

Furthermore, studies suggested that nutritional care has a major impact on HAPI prevention and management (Citty et al., 2019; Litchford et al., 2020; Moore & Webster, 2018).

Patient, Family, and Caregiver Education

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to patient, family, and caregiver education. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, patient, family, and caregiver education. Patient, family, and caregiver education is warranted throughout the hospital admission (Team et al., 2020; Whitty et al., 2017). Healthcare providers must identify patient ability and motivation to prevent HAPIs, partner with patients, family, and caregivers to ensure that HAPI interventions are facilitated with appropriate pain management (Team et al., 2020; Whitty et al., 2017). Furthermore, healthcare providers should assess the patient's ability and motivation to HAPI prevention and ensure that comfort levels are managed to facilitate activities and repositioning (Deakin et al., 2020; Hekmatpou et al., 2018). Patient, family, and caregiver involvement provided autonomy to patient's personal goals of care (Deakin et al., 2020; Hekmatpou et al., 2018).

Repositioning

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to repositioning frequencies and positions to prevent HAPIs. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, decubitus ulcer, repositioning, positions, and frequencies. Repositioning of patients is key in HAPI prevention and recommended in all clinical practice guidelines (Avsar et al., 2020; De Meyer et al., 2019; Moore & Patton, 2019). However,

recent evidence reflected a more patient-centered, individualized plan of care to prevent HAPIs (Gillespie et al., 2020).

Clinical practice guidelines recommended that the patient's ability to reposition themselves would guide the healthcare provider's decision-making regarding the frequency of repositioning (Buğdaycı & Paker, 2021; NPIAP, 2019; Gillespie et al., 2021; Schünemann et al., 2019). Evidence suggests a lack of robust evaluation to conclude whether a two-hourly versus four-hourly repositioning regimen was more effective than the other for HAPI prevention interventions (Buğdaycı & Paker, 2021; Gillespie et al., 2021; Schünemann et al., 2019). Overall, repositioning patients and other HAPI prevention interventions can reduce pressure injuries in critically ill patients (Alderden et al., 2020; Alshahrani et al., 2021).

Nursing Early Mobility Program

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to early mobility related to HAPI prevention. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms utilized included, in various combinations, with limiters: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, early mobility, nursing, and nurse-led.

The project facility developed a program for early mobility in the ICU using trained nurses and patient care technicians to perform acute early mobility interventions. Early mobility aimed to reduce HAPI incidence and factors associated with ICU deconditioning by using specially trained personnel (Alderden et al., 2020; Alshahrani et al., 2021). Implementing an early mobility program improves patients' overall functions, promotes timely ventilator weaning, and expands patients' endurance (Lin et al., 2020; Klein et al., 2018). Furthermore, early mobility programs decrease hospital LOS, minimize hospital-acquired conditions, and prevent

HAPI incidences, thus reducing hospital costs (Alderden et al., 2020; Alshahrani et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2020; Klein et al., 2018).

Algorithm Integration

A literature review was conducted to gather research related to the use of an algorithm to prevent HAPIs. The following databases were searched: CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library. The search terms included: HAPI, pressure injury, pressure ulcer, decubitus ulcer, prevention, algorithm, evidence-based, and healthcare.

Evidence showed that patient care was provided more effectively and efficiently with algorithms based on evidence-based clinical practice guidelines to prevent HAPIs (De Carvalho et al., 2017; Mansfield et al., 2019; Yilmazer & Bulut, 2019). Various studies revealed that when using a HAPI prevention algorithm, the rate of the number of HAPIs decreased considerably (De Carvalho et al., 2017; Mansfield et al., 2019; Yilmazer & Bulut, 2019). The HAPI prevention algorithm served as a visual roadmap for the nurses. It guided the participants' decision-making when planning care for patients. Moreover, the single-page algorithm addressed the lack of nurses' time to review the lengthy policies on pressure injury management and early mobility protocol (De Carvalho et al., 2017; Mansfield et al., 2019).

PARIHS Framework Integration

A literature review was conducted utilizing CINAHL, PubMed, and Google Scholar to review the literature regarding the use of the PARIHS framework and how it has been utilized to adopt new evidence and clinical guidelines in clinical practice. Search terms included PARIHS, guideline implementation, implementation, and barriers. The limits of this search were articles that were published between 2017 and 2022 in English.

The PARIHS model was applicable to multiple healthcare settings (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2020; Gunningberg et al., 2018; Sving et al., 2020). Studies examining staff empowerment, workflow processes, and guideline development demonstrated the efficacy of the PARIHS model and the importance of the elements of evidence, context, and facilitation (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2020; Gunningberg et al., 2018; Sving et al., 2020). One study utilizing the PARIHS framework to guide HAPI prevention processes resulted in HAPI reduction (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2020). This report demonstrated that the effective translation of evidence into practice in an acute care setting with strong facilitation resulted in systemwide practice change (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2020).

An interprofessional plan of care identified individualized patient care goals and interventions in a collaborative manner (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2020; Fulbrook et al., 2019; Lovegrove et al., 2021). Healthcare providers, nurses, patients, family, and caregivers play a key role in preventing HAPIs with multiple daily decisions in clinical practice that directly affect the outcomes of care (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2020; Fulbrook et al., 2019; Tirgari et al., 2018). The integration of the care plan interventions into an algorithm can provide step-by-step guides for clinical decision-making (Carvalho et al., 2017; Mansfield et al., 2019). Furthermore, the application of the PARIHS model can result in a significant decrease in HAPIs and positive practice changes that can lead to improved patient outcomes (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2020; Gunningberg et al., 2018; Sving et al., 2020).

Methods

The methods section outlined the processes used to translate evidence into practice systematically. Specific aims of this quality improvement (QI) project were: 1) to evaluate nurses' views of HAPI prevention practices, 2) to decrease the incidence of HAPIs for critically ill adults in an 8-bed ICU by 10% over one month by developing an algorithm for HAPI prevention and providing education to the nurses.

The project's methodology covered the components of the project's approach, sample and setting, procedures for recruitment, and data collection (Roush, 2018). It included the instruments and tools used in data collection and management. The methodology section represented the project's validity, reliability, and ability to use the QI tool confidently (Roush, 2018). The project's methods were dependable and replicable, which increased reliability (Bonnell & Smith, 2018). The project leader utilized a truthful representation of the data via anonymous survey tools, which increased the project's validity (Bonnell & Smith, 2018). The integration of the care plan interventions into the HAPI Prevention Algorithm illustrated a clear process for clinical decision-making (Carvalho et al., 2017; Mansfield et al., 2019). Furthermore, the application of the PARIHS model resulted in a significant decrease in HAPIs, and positive practice changes led to improved patient outcomes (Bakarat-Johnson et al., 2020; Gunningberg et al., 2018; Sving et al., 2020). The HAPI prevention algorithm tool was used as a visual guideline for participants to prevent HAPIs.

Design

A quality improvement approach, supported by evidence, was used to meet the project's goals. The adaptation of the PARIHS framework guided all aspects of the HAPI algorithm. The

anonymous surveys, adapted from AHRQ, were used to collect data from staff nurses working in the pilot unit and identify the nurses' views on HAPI prevention.

Setting

The project was implemented in an 8-bed Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU) at an acute care hospital. This world-renowned academic medical center is a nonprofit organization located in Los Angeles, California. The facility has no emergency department; however, it operates 24 hours a day, seven days a week. The project facility accepts most insurance plans and collaborates with many local and national managed care networks. It provides resources to community hospitals for complex medical and surgical cases, focusing on tertiary and quaternary care.

Participants

Access to nursing staff to participate in the QI project was sought from the Director of Nursing and the Nurse Manager. A list of participants' work email addresses was received from the nurse manager. The surveys were sent to 31 nurses from the pilot unit. Seventeen ICU nurses participated in this project. During the staff meetings, the project lead explained the QI project to all participants. The participants were registered nurses (RN) working in the pilot unit, Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU). The RNs were allowed to discontinue their participation at any time. Participants were not part of a special subject population. The principal investigator had no relations, authority, or position of power over the participants. The participants were informed of the risks and benefits of their involvement in the project. Upon agreement to participate in the project, the participants were informed that their participation was optional and no identifying information would be collected. The HAPI prevention algorithm project information was provided to participants through emails, staff meetings, and UPC meetings. Participants were

informed how to reach the project lead via email and mobile telephone. Inclusion criteria were all full-time, part-time, and per diem staff nurses working in the MICU were invited to participate. Exclusion criteria were contract nurses, registry nurses, and float pool nurses. Certified nurse assistants, telemetry monitor technicians, and patient care technicians were excluded from the surveys.

Recruitment and Screening Process

The participants were recruited via the staff meeting hosted by the nurse manager, and work emails (Email Invitation: Pre-Intervention Survey in Appendix H) were provided by the participants' nurse manager. An informational cover sheet (Appendix F for Informational Cover Letter) was emailed to the participants for more instructions and information on the study's background, purpose, risks, and benefits.

Institutional Review Board Approval

Organizational Institutional review board (IRB) approval from the project facility was sought and granted. Following the project facility's approval, Institutional review board (IRB) approval from California State University, Los Angeles, was secured before the project commenced at the study facility, as shown in Appendix B. The project lead guaranteed the anonymity of the participants and the participating institutions. The data was constantly treated as confidential. Surveys were not labeled with personal identifying information (e.g., name, email address, IP address) or a code the research team can link to personal identifying information. Results from this project did not identify any of the participants. All information gathered in this project was confidential. The project had a minimal risk for loss of confidentiality as no personal contact or identifying information (ex., name, number, email,

signature, etc.) was asked or collected during the start and completion of participation in the project.

Measures

Outcome measures were used to determine whether there was an improvement in the nursing knowledge and views on HAPI prevention. Outcome measures were the percentage of nurses who agreed to HAPI prevention interventions by one month. The balancing measure was the decrease of HAPIs in the MICU by 10% from the baseline month. Data for each of these measures were recorded before implementing the education to obtain baseline data and ending one week after implementation. Data were converted to diverging charts once sufficient data was collected.

Procedure

The evidence-based algorithm elements were derived from the hospital's policies on skin care, tissue injury management, and nursing mobility protocol. A flow chart was created to list all the HAPI prevention interventions. The algorithm elements were created in collaboration with the UPC members from the pilot unit, CNS, and WCCNE. The PARIHS model guided the creation of the algorithm. The recent review of the literature provided clinical evidence for each HAPI prevention intervention listed in the algorithm.

The surveys were given to the participants using Qualtrics links via work emails. The surveys used a 5-point Likert-like scale and were given before the staff education on the HAPI prevention algorithm tool. The response options allowed a full range of possible views on HAPI prevention. The term pressure ulcer on the surveys was replaced with pressure injury to add more clarity to the questions. Participants were educated about the HAPI prevention tool (Appendix E) during their unit practice council (UPC) and staff meetings. The surveys were given to the

participants after the education on the HAPI prevention tool. The online surveys were disseminated using Qualtrics (Qualtrics Survey in Appendix G).

The survey method removed the influence of the project lead over the participants. The anonymous survey created distance between the project lead and the participants. This allowed the participants to answer questions openly and genuinely. The use of structured questions reduces participant bias. The advantages of the surveys for this QI project were the low cost and the ability to reach all the possible participants from the pilot unit. Disadvantages include the response rate of only 57% and the risk of participant bias. This led to a sample not representative of the participant views being assessed, affecting the results and conclusions drawn from the study.

Data Collection

The DNP student collected the survey data through the project facility's Qualtrics program. Microsoft Excel reports were generated through Qualtrics. Data values were entered in the IBM Statistical Package Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics, Version 28, for analysis. The monthly HAPI rates were retrieved from the pilot unit's National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators (NDNQI) report.

Data Management/Storage Plan

The de-identified data from the completed surveys were only viewed and accessed by the project lead. All data were stored in a secured, password-enabled computer. The data will be kept and stored for three years following the completion of the project and destroyed thereafter. The project lead used a computer protected by encryption, strong login, and a Duo security authentication system.

Results

The initial steps of the HAPI prevention project were accomplished in three weeks. A pre-intervention survey was provided to the participants on November 17, 2022, to December 1, 2022. The pre-intervention survey (Appendix H) was provided to the participants prior to receiving the education and the roll-out of the algorithm. Completion of the pre-intervention survey was voluntary. Of the 31 MICU nurses who received the pre-intervention survey, 17 completed it (Pre-Intervention Survey Results in Appendix K), representing a 57% response rate. Thirty-one MICU nurses attended the staff meeting on December 6, 2023, where the DNP student provided education on the HAPI prevention algorithm tool.

The post-intervention survey (Email Invitation: Post-Intervention Survey in Appendix I) was sent and completed by 17 MICU nurses over three weeks ending on January 6, 2023. Per instructions provided, the MICU nurses did not provide any identifying information when completing their surveys, nor were responses coded; thus, it is unknown whether the same 17 participants responded to the pre- and post-intervention surveys. The IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics, Version 28, and Microsoft Excel were used to analyze the results. An independent sample *t*-Test (*t*-Test Results in Appendix M) was calculated to determine the difference between the means for the individual items of the pre-intervention survey results and post-intervention survey results (Post-Intervention Survey Results in Appendix L).

The overall HAPIs in the pilot unit had a 50% decrease from the baseline data after the education on HAPI prevention algorithm was provided to the participants. The engagement from the UPC members increased staff empowerment in clinical practice change in a collaborative way. The shared governance secured mutual understanding in adherence to change. Evidence

suggests an ongoing education and revision of the change tool is necessary for sustainability of change (Dalvand et al., 2018; Gedamu et al., 2021; Shiferaw et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022).

The 17 participants who responded to the pre-intervention statement, “All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries” ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 1.32$), were compared to the participants in the post-intervention group to the same question ($M = 4.82$, $SD = 0.39$). Results demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in their understanding of the increased risks of pressure injury on patients, $t(18.83) = -2.12$, $p = .048$. There was a 42% increase in participants who strongly agreed that all patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries.

The same 17 participants who responded to the pre-intervention statement that their clinical judgment is better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to them ($M = 2.88$, $SD = 1.36$) were compared to the participants in the post-intervention group ($M = 1.71$, $SD = 0.92$). Results revealed a statistically significant improvement in their clinical judgment, $t(28.05) = 2.95$, $p = .006$. After introducing the HAPI prevention algorithm tool, most participants acknowledged that they did not know all the interventions to prevent HAPIs. There was a 146% increase in participants who strongly disagreed that their clinical judgment was better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to participants.

Analyzing participants’ opinions that patients tended not to get as many pressure injuries nowadays, the pre-intervention group response ($M = 4.29$, $SD = 1.36$) when compared to post-intervention group ($M = 5.00$, $SD = 0.00$), indicated a statistically significant improvement in their perception, $t(16.00) = -2.14$, $p = .040$. There was a 43% increase in participants who strongly agreed that pressure injury risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay at the hospital.

Overall, survey results demonstrated that the MICU nurses' perceptions improved from the pre-intervention to post-intervention survey. All items moved towards evidence-based views, indicating clinical significance. Four items indicated statistical significance, while three others approached statistical significance. Post-intervention, 65% of the participants strongly disagreed with the statement that patients tended not to get as many pressure injuries currently versus in the past, $t(26.95) = 1.69, p = .103$. Seventy-one percent of participants disagreed with the statement that pressure injury treatment is a greater priority than pressure injury prevention, $t(32) = 1.69, p = .102$, which approached statistical significance.

Discussion

Pressure injury prevention is a complex issue that many hospitals attempt to address. There have been efforts to improve HAPI prevention practices by using a systematic approach to promote change. The DNP project involved several modifications to action steps designed to improve and prevent HAPIs. Updating clinicians' knowledge and assessing their views was essential to assess existing knowledge that may have been undermined by efforts to change HAPI prevention (Dalvand et al., 2018; Gedamu et al., 2021; Shiferaw et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022).

Although the survey received only 17 responses, statistical significance was realized for three items, and two additional approached statistical significance, indicating an important change in beliefs and perceptions. The three survey questions that showed statistical significance after the HAPI prevention algorithm education were: 1) All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries. 2) My clinical Judgment is better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to me. And 3) Pressure injury risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay in the hospital. One hundred percent of the participants agreed that all patients were at potential risk of developing pressure injuries. The nurses disagreed that their clinical judgment was better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to them (83%), this was a significant increase from 30%. Furthermore, 100% of the participants agreed that pressure injury risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay in the hospital, which was an increase from 83%. All three survey questions showed statistical significance ($p=.048$, $p=.006$, $p=.040$).

Two additional results approached statistical significance. There was a 50% reduction in HAPI rate in the MICU after implementing the HAPI prevention algorithm. Seventy-eight

percent of the participants disagreed with the statement that patients tended not to get as many pressure injuries ($p = .103$). Eighty-nine percent of the participants disagreed with the statement that pressure injury treatment was a greater priority than pressure injury prevention ($p = .102$). Both results presented clinical significance in preventing HAPIs in the healthcare environment. However, despite various evidence-based strategies and clinical preventative interventions, sustainability continued to be a challenge (Klinga et al., 2018; Lennox et al., 2018; Shelton et al., 2018). Organizational sustainability requires continuously adapting the practice change (Klinga et al., 2018; Lennox et al., 2018; Shelton et al., 2018)

The changes from the pre-intervention to the post-intervention surveys indicate a change in beliefs and perceptions but don't necessarily translate to patient outcomes (Fontaine et al., 2018). However, in this case, standard monthly tracking demonstrated a decrease in identified pressure injuries. This measure should be closely monitored to identify trends and determine the need for early re-education.

Recommendations

Despite various evidence-based strategies and clinical preventative interventions, sustainability continues to be challenging (Klinga et al., 2018; Lennox et al., 2018; Shelton et al., 2018). Organizational sustainability requires that staff continuously adhere to the introduced change (Klinga et al., 2018; Lennox et al., 2018). Continuous refinement of the algorithm content was needed to maintain sustainability (Klinga et al., 2018; Lennox et al., 2018; Shelton et al., 2018). The project lead continued to refine the algorithm and provided a month of education in the pilot unit about the HAPI prevention algorithm. The utilization of the HAPI prevention algorithm heightened awareness of the problem and provided a standardized guideline for care (Klinga et al., 2018; Lennox et al., 2018; Shelton et al., 2018).

Further assessment was needed to investigate the views of nurses regarding whether pressure injury prevention should be explored. The expenditure of providing nursing education should be targeted appropriately to add value to the participant's knowledge of HAPI prevention. Data were collected for four months; however, a longer period of data collection would have provided information to determine if the practice change was continued or if additional reinforcement was needed. Furthermore, the QI project used a pilot unit for surveys; hence, the project lead was unable to assess the facility-wide perceptions and educational deficits regarding HAPIs. Extending the surveys to all nurses in the project facility can provide better data results and lead to a greater reduction in pressure injuries.

Implications

The results from this QI project suggested that views related to HAPI prevention can be changeable. The knowledge and views are vital for advancing practice in HAPI prevention. This QI project highlighted that positive attitudes and views were insufficient to ensure a practice change occurred. Strategies to introduce change must acknowledge the complex nature of change management, where staff can be empowered. Improving the nurses' knowledge of HAPI prevention not only contributed to the quality of care, but also shortened the LOS, prevented readmission, decreased hospitalization costs, and improved the patient's quality of life (Dalvand et al., 2018; Gedamu et al., 2021; Shiferaw et al., 2020).

Limitations

There are several limitations to this QI project. It was implemented in a small pilot unit, excluding the remaining units of the project facility. Only forty-five percent of the staff in the pilot unit did not complete the surveys; therefore, their views on HAPI prevention were unclear. The overall views and knowledge of nurses about HAPI prevention were difficult to determine

since there was only a 57% response rate. The anonymous survey questions made it difficult to determine who completed the form and who did not. Furthermore, the project lead was not present when the surveys were distributed, which removed the resource to explain areas of concern regarding the survey by participants.

Conclusions

Regular education sessions and sustainable training on HAPI prevention were warranted to ensure quality patient care (Dalvand et al., 2018; Gedamu et al., 2021; Shiferaw et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2022). Using a single-page algorithm provided a visual aid to the nurses who lacked time to read the multi-page policies (De Carvalho et al., 2017; Mansfield et al., 2019; Yilmazer & Bulut, 2019). Incorporating multidisciplinary collaboration into the algorithm ensured support from other disciplines (De Carvalho et al., 2017; Mansfield et al., 2019; Yilmazer & Bulut, 2019). Changes from the pre-intervention to the post-intervention survey indicated a change in nurse views. The results translated to positive patient outcomes demonstrated by the significant reduction in HAPI rates.

References

- Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (2022). Preventing pressure ulcers in hospitals. <https://www.ahrq.gov/patient-safety/settings/hospital/resource/pressureulcer/tool/index.html>
- Alderden, J. G., Shibily, F., & Cowan, L. (2020). Best practice in pressure injury prevention among critical care patients. *Critical Care Nursing Clinics*, 32(4), 489-500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cnc.2020.08.001>
- Allingstrup, M. J., Kondrup, J., Wiis, J., Claudius, C., Pedersen, U. G., Hein-Rasmussen, R., & Perner, A. (2017). Early goal-directed nutrition versus standard of care in adult intensive care patients: The single-centre, randomised, outcome assessor-blinded EAT-ICU trial. *Intensive Care Medicine*, 43(11), 1637-1647. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00134-017-4880-3>
- Aloweni, F., Lim, M. L., Chua, T. L., Tan, S. B., Lian, S. B., & Ang, S. Y. (2017). A randomised controlled trial to evaluate the incremental effectiveness of a prophylactic dressing and fatty acids oil in the prevention of pressure injuries. *Wound Practice & Research: Journal of the Australian Wound Management Association*, 25(1), 24-34. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.745447724886743>
- Alshahrani, B., Sim, J., & Middleton, R. (2021). Nursing interventions for pressure injury prevention among critically ill patients: A systematic review. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 30(15-16), 2151-2168. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15709>
- Armour, D. J., Preston-Hsu, E., & Tailor, Y. (2019). Management of pressure ulcers and pressure-related injury. *Current Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Reports*, 7(2), 170-177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40141-019-00222-x>

- Avsar, P., Moore, Z., Patton, D., O'Connor, T., Budri, A. M., & Nugent, L. (2020). Repositioning for preventing pressure ulcers: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Wound Care*, 29(9), 496-508. <https://doi.org/10.12968/jowc.2020.29.9.496>
- Bakarat-Johnson, M., Lai, M., Wand, T., Coyer, F., & White, K. (2020). Systemwide practice change program to combat hospital-acquired pressure injuries. *Journal of Nursing Care Quality*, 35(1), 51-57. <https://doi:10.1097/NCQ.0000000000000395>
- Bergstrom, A., Ehrenberg, A., Eldh, A. C., Graham, I. D., Gustafsson, K., Harvey, G., Hunter, S., Kitson, A., Rycroft-Malone, J., & Wallin, L. (2020). The use of the PARIHS framework in implementation research and practice – A citation analysis of the literature. *Implementation Science*, 15(1). 68. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-020-01003-0>
- Black, J. M. (2019). Root cause analysis for hospital-acquired pressure injury. *Journal of Wound Ostomy & Continence Nursing*, 46(4), 298-304. <https://doi.org/10.1097/won.0000000000000546>
- Bonnel, W., & Smith, K. V. (2018). *Proposal writing for clinical nursing and DNP projects*. Springer publishing company.
- Buğdaycı, D. S., & Paker, N. (2021). Is repositioning effective for pressure injury prevention in adults? A Cochrane Review summary with commentary. *Turkish Journal of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 67(4), 526–529. <https://dx.doi.org/10.5606%2Fftird.2021.10235>
- Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services. (2023). Cross-setting pressure ulcer measurement and quality improvement. <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Quality-Initiatives-Patient-Assessment-Instruments/Post-Acute-Care-Quality-Initiatives/Cross-Setting-Pressure-Ulcer-Measurement-and-Quality-Improvement>

- Citty, S. W., Cowan, L. J., Wingfield, Z., & Stechmiller, J. (2019). Optimizing nutrition care for pressure injuries in hospitalized patients. *Advances in Wound Care*, 8(7), 309-322.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/wound.2018.0925>
- Coyer, F., Cook, J. L., Doubrovsky, A., Vann, A., & McNamara, G. (2022). Exploring medical device-related pressure injuries in a single intensive care setting: A longitudinal point prevalence study. *Intensive and Critical Care Nursing*, 68, 103155.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iccn.2021.103155>
- Cox, J., Edsberg, L. E., Koloms, K., & VanGilder, C. A. (2022). Pressure injuries in critical care patients in US hospitals: Results of the International Pressure Ulcer Prevalence Survey. *Journal of Wound, Ostomy and Continence Nursing*, 49(1), 21-28.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/WON.0000000000000834>
- Dalvand, S., Ebadi, A., & Gheshlagh, R. G. (2018). Nurses' knowledge on pressure injury prevention: A systematic review and meta-analysis based on the Pressure Ulcer Knowledge Assessment Tool. *Clinical, Cosmetic and Investigational Dermatology*, 218(11) 613-620. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ccid.s186381>
- De Carvalho, M. R. F., Salomé, G. M., & Ferreira, L. M. (2017). Construction and validation of algorithm for treatment of pressure injury. *Journal of Nursing UFPE/Revista de Enfermagem UFPE*, 11(10).
- De Meyer, D., Van Hecke, A., Verhaeghe, S., & Beeckman, D. (2019). PROTECT–Trial: A cluster RCT to study the effectiveness of a repositioning aid and tailored repositioning to increase repositioning compliance. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 75(5), 1085-1098.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13932>

- Deakin, J., Gillespie, B. M., Chaboyer, W., Nieuwenhoven, P., & Latimer, S. (2020). An education intervention care bundle to improve hospitalised patients' pressure injury prevention knowledge: A before and after study. *Wound Practice & Research: Journal of the Australian Wound Management Association*, 28(4), 154-162.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.33235/wpr.28.4.154-162>
- Forni, C., D'Alessandro, F., Gallerani, P., Genco, R., Bolzon, A., Bombino, C., Mini, S., Rocchegiani, L., Notarnicola, T., Vitulli, A., Amodeo, A., Celli, G., & Taddia, P. (2018). Effectiveness of using a new polyurethane foam multi-layer dressing in the sacral area to prevent the onset of pressure ulcer in the elderly with hip fractures: A pragmatic randomised controlled trial. *International Wound Journal*, 15(3), 383-390.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/iwj.12875>
- Fulbrook, P., Lawrence, P., & Miles, S. (2019). Australian nurses' knowledge of pressure injury prevention and management: A cross-sectional survey. *Journal of Wound, Ostomy and Continence Nursing*, 46(2), 106. <https://doi.org/10.1097/won.0000000000000508>
- Gedamu, H., Abate, T., Ayalew, E., Tegenaw, A., Birhanu, M., & Tafere, Y. (2021). Level of nurses' knowledge on pressure ulcer prevention: A systematic review and meta-analysis study in Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 7(7), e07648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07648>
- Gillespie, B. M., Walker, R. M., Latimer, S. L., Thalib, L., Whitty, J. A., McInnes, E., & Chaboyer, W. P. (2020). Repositioning for pressure injury prevention in adults. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 6(6), CD009958.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd009958.pub3>
- Gillespie, B. M., Walker, R. M., Latimer, S. L., Thalib, L., Whitty, J. A., McInnes, E., Lockwood, I., & Chaboyer, W. P. (2021). Repositioning for pressure injury prevention in

- adults: An abridged Cochrane systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 120, 103976. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2021.103976>
- Goodman, L., Khemani, E., Cacao, F., Yoon, J., Burkoski, V., Jarrett, S. & Hall, T. N. (2018). A comparison of hospital-acquired pressure injuries in intensive care and non-intensive care units: A multifaceted quality improvement initiative. *BMJ Open Quality*, 7(4), e000425. <http://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-000425>
- Gunningberg, L., Baath, C., & Sving, E. (2018). Staff's perceptions of a pressure mapping system to prevent pressure injuries in a hospital ward: A qualitative study. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 26(2), 140-147. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.12526>
- Hahnel, E., El Genedy, M., Tomova-Simitchieva, T., Hauß, A., Stroux, A., Lechner, A., Richter, C., Akdeniz, M., Blume-Peytavi, U., Lober, N., & Kottner, J. (2020). The effectiveness of two silicone dressings for sacral and heel pressure ulcer prevention compared with no dressings in high-risk intensive care unit patients: A randomized controlled parallel-group trial. *British Journal of Dermatology*, 183(2), 256-264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.18621>
- The Joint Commission. (2023). *Quick safety issue: Preventing pressure injuries*. <https://www.jointcommission.org/resources/news-and-multimedia/newsletters/newsletters/quick-safety/quick-safety-issue-25-preventing-pressure-injuries/>
- Kitson, A. L., Rycroft-Malone, J., Harvey, G., McCormack, B., Seers, K., & Titchen, A. (2008). Evaluating the successful implementation of evidence into practice using PARIHS framework: Theoretical and practical challenges. *Implementation Science*, 3(1), 1-12. <https://doi:10.1186/1748-5908-3-1>

- Klein, L. M., Young, D., Feng, D., Lavezza, A., Hiser, S., Daley, K. N., & Hoyer, E. H. (2018). Increasing patient mobility through an individualized goal-centered hospital mobility program: A quasi-experimental quality improvement project. *Nursing Outlook*, 66(3), 254-262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2018.02.006>
- Klinga, C., Hasson, H., Andreen Sachs, M., & Hansson, J. (2018). Understanding the dynamics of sustainable change: A 20-year case study of integrated health and social care. *BioMed Central Health Services Research*, 18(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3061-6>
- Latimer, S., Chaboyer, W., Thalib, L., McInnes, E., Bucknall, T., & Gillespie, B. (2021). Prevalence and predictors of pressure injuries among older hospitalised adult patients: An Australian multi-site study. *Wound Practice & Research*, 29(2). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.14967>
- Lee, K., Murphy, P. B., Ingves, M. V., Duncan, A., DeRose, G., Dubois, L., Forbes, T., & Power, A. (2017). Randomized clinical trial of negative pressure wound therapy for high-risk groin wounds in lower extremity revascularization. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 66(6), 1814-1819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2017.06.084>
- Lennox, L., Maher, L., & Reed, J. (2018). Navigating the sustainability landscape: A systematic review of sustainability approaches in healthcare. *Implementation Science*, 13(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-017-0707-4>
- Lin, F., Wu, Z., Song, B., Coyer, F., & Chaboyer, W. (2020). The effectiveness of multicomponent pressure injury prevention programs in adult intensive care patients: A systematic review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 102, 103483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2019.103483>

- Litchford, M. D. (2020). Putting the 2019 nutrition recommendations for pressure injury prevention and treatment into practice. *Advances in Skin & Wound Care*, 33(9), 462-468. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.asw.0000688412.05627.96>
- Lovegrove, J., Fulbrook, P., Miles, S. J., & Steele, M. (2021). Effectiveness of interventions to prevent pressure injury in adults admitted to acute hospital settings: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 122, 104027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2021.104027>
- Mansfield, S., Obraczka, K., & Roy, S. (2019). Pressure injury prevention: A survey. *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering*, 13, 352-368. <https://doi.org/10.1109/rbme.2019.2927200>
- Mervis, J. S., & Phillips, T. J. (2019). Pressure ulcers: Pathophysiology, epidemiology, risk factors, and presentation. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, 81(4), 881-890. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaad.2018.12.069>
- Moore, Z. E., & Webster, J. (2018). Dressings and topical agents for preventing pressure ulcers. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 12(12), CD009362. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd009362.pub3>
- Moore, Z. E., & Patton, D. (2019). Risk assessment tools for the prevention of pressure ulcers. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd006471.pub4>
- Morrison, A., Madden, C., & Messmer, J. (2022). Management of chronic wounds. *Primary Care: Clinics in Office Practice*, 49(1), 85-98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pop.2021.10.009>
- Munoz, N., Posthauer, M. E., Cereda, E., Schols, J. M., & Haesler, E. (2020). The role of nutrition for pressure injury prevention and healing: The 2019 International Clinical

Practice Guideline Recommendations. *Advances in Skin & Wound Care*, 33(3), 123-136.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.ASW.0000653144.90739.ad>

- Niederauer, M. Q., Michalek, J. E., & Armstrong, D. G. (2017). A prospective, randomized, double-blind multicenter study comparing continuous diffusion of oxygen therapy to sham therapy in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers. *Journal of Diabetes Science and Technology*, 11(5), 883-891. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1177%2F1932296817695574>
- Palanski, M. E., Thomas, J. S., Hammond, M. M., Lester, G. V., & Clapp-Smith, R. (2021). Being a leader and doing leadership: The cross-domain impact of family and friends on leader identity and leader behaviors at work. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 28(3), 273-286. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15480518211005452>
- Pickham, D., Berte, N., Pihulic, M., Valdez, A., Mayer, B., & Desai, M. (2018). Effect of a wearable patient sensor on care delivery for preventing pressure injuries in acutely ill adults: A pragmatic randomized clinical trial (LS-HAPI study). *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 80, 12-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2017.12.012>
- Razzaghi, R., Pourbagheri, H., Momen-Heravi, M., Bahmani, F., Shadi, J., Soleimani, Z., & Asemi, Z. (2017). The effects of vitamin D supplementation on wound healing and metabolic status in patients with diabetic foot ulcer: A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Journal of Diabetes and its Complications*, 31(4), 766-772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacom.2016.06.017>
- Roberts, N. A., Janda, M., Stover, A. M., Alexander, K. E., Wyld, D., & Mudge, A. (2021). PROMs/PREMs in clinical practice implementation science work group. The utility of the implementation science framework "Integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services" (i-PARIHS) and the facilitator role for introducing

- patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) in a medical oncology outpatient department. *Quality Life Research*, 30(11), 3063-3071. <https://doi:10.1007/s11136-020-02669-1>
- Sala, J. J., Mayampurath, A., Solmos, S., Vonderheid, S. C., Banas, M., D'Souza, A., & LaFond, C. (2021). Predictors of pressure injury development in critically ill adults: A retrospective cohort study. *Intensive and Critical Care Nursing*, 62, 102924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iccn.2020.102924>
- Scheffler, M., Koranyi, S., Meissner, W., Strauss, B., & Rosendahl, J. (2018). Efficacy of non-pharmacological interventions for procedural pain relief in adults undergoing burn wound care: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Burns*, 44(7), 1709-1720. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.burns.2017.11.019>
- Schünemann, H. J., Higgins, J. P., Vist, G. E., Glasziou, P., Akl, E. A., Skoetz, N., & Guyatt, G. (2019). Cochrane GRADEing Methods Group (formerly Applicability and Recommendations Methods Group) and the Cochrane Statistical Methods Group. Completing 'summary of findings' tables and grading the certainty of the evidence. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions*, 375-402. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119536604.ch14>
- Shelton, R. C., Cooper, B. R., & Stirman, S. W. (2018). The sustainability of evidence-based interventions and practices in public health and health care. *Annual Review of Public Health*, 39, 55-76. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-040617-014731>
- Short, W., Olutoye, O., Padon, B., Parikh, U., Colchado, D., Vangapandu, H., Shams, S., Chi, T., Jung, J., & Balaji, S. (2022). Advances in non-invasive biosensing measures to monitor

wound healing progression. *Preprints*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.20944/preprints202203.0293.v1>

- Squitieri, L., Ganda, D. A., Mangione, C. M., Needleman, J., Romano, P. S., Saliba, D., Ko, C. Y., & Waxman, D. A. (2018). Consistency of pressure injury documentation across interfacility transfers. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, 27(3), 182–189. <https://doi:10.1136/bmjqs-2017-006726>
- Sving, E., Baath, C., Gunningberg, L., & Bjorn, C. (2020). The experiences of operating room teams working with real-time feedback of interface pressure to prevent pressure injuries – A feasibility study. *Perioperative Care and Operating Room Management*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcorn.2020.100096>
- Team, V., Bouguettaya, A., Richards, C., Turnour, L., Jones, A., Teede, H., & Weller, C. D. (2020). Patient education materials on pressure injury prevention in hospitals and health services in Victoria, Australia: Availability and content analysis. *International Wound Journal*, 17(2), 370-379. <https://doi.org/10.1111/iwj.13281>
- Tirgari, B., Mirshekari, L., & Forouzi, M. A. (2018). Pressure injury prevention: Knowledge and attitudes of Iranian intensive care nurses. *Advances in Skin & Wound Care*, 31(4), 1-8. <https://doi:10.1097/01.ASW.0000530848.50085.ef>
- Rycroft-Malone, J. (2004). The PARIHS framework for guiding the implementation of evidence-based practice. *Journal of Nursing Care Quality*, 19(4), 297-304. <https://doi:10.1097/00001786-200410000-00002>
- Shiferaw, W. S., Aynalem, Y. A., & Akalu, T. Y. (2020). Prevalence of pressure ulcers among hospitalized adult patients in Ethiopia: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *BioMed Central Dermatology*, 20, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12895-020-00112-z>

- Walker, R. M., Gillespie, B. M., McInnes, E., Moore, Z., Eskes, A. M., Patton, D., Harbeck, E., White, C., Scott, I., & Chaboyer, W. (2020). Prevention and treatment of pressure injuries: A meta-synthesis of Cochrane Reviews. *Journal of Tissue Viability*, 29(4), 227-243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtv.2020.05.004>
- Walker, R., Huxley, L., Juttner, M., Burmeister, E., Scott, J., & Aitken, L. M. (2017). A pilot randomized controlled trial using prophylactic dressings to minimize sacral pressure injuries in high-risk hospitalized patients. *Clinical Nursing Research*, 26(4), 484-503. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1054773816629689>
- Ward, M. M., Baloh, J., Zhu, X., & Stewart, G. L. (2017). Promoting action on research implementation in health services framework applied to TeamSTEPPS implementation in small rural hospitals. *Healthcare Management Review*, 42(1), 2–13. <https://doi:10.1097/HMR.0000000000000086>
- Whitty, J. A., McInnes, E., Bucknall, T., Webster, J., Gillespie, B. M., Banks, M., Thalib, L., Wallis, M., Cumsille, J., Roberts, S., & Chaboyer, W. (2017). The cost-effectiveness of a patient centred pressure ulcer prevention care bundle: Findings from the INTACT cluster randomised trial. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 75, 35-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2017.06.014>
- Wu, J., Wang, B., Zhu, L., & Jia, X. (2022). Nurses' knowledge on pressure ulcer prevention: An updated systematic review and meta-analysis based on the Pressure Ulcer Knowledge Assessment Tool (PUKAT). *Frontiers in Public Health*, 3050. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.964680>
- Yıldırım, S., Özener, H. Ö., Doğan, B., & Kuru, B. (2018). Effect of topically applied hyaluronic acid on pain and palatal epithelial wound healing: An examiner-masked, randomized,

controlled clinical trial. *Journal of Periodontology*, 89(1), 36-45.

<https://doi.org/10.1902/jop.2017.170105>

Yilmazer, T., & Bulut, H. (2019). Evaluating the effects of a pressure injury prevention algorithm. *Advances in Skin & Wound Care*, 32(6), 278-284.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.ASW.0000553597.18658.6b>

Appendix A
Institutional Approval Letter

Keck Medicine
of USC

May 17, 2022

Keck Medicine of **USC**

This letter represents my support for the proposed project on hospital-acquired pressure injury prevention by Melanie Cariker, the nurse leading the evidence-based practice project. The project's purpose reflects the Magnet culture at Keck Medical Center of USC in empowering our shared governance and utilizing an evidence-based algorithm to improve patient outcomes. Adoption of the new algorithm will ensure that hospital-acquired pressure injuries are prevented and appropriately managed by our multidisciplinary team. Thus, this will lead to improved patient outcomes.

I lend my full support to this project for Melanie Cariker's Doctor of Nursing Practice project with Dr. Elizabeth Winokur as her chair and team lead.

Sincerely,

Stephanie L. Hall, MD, MHA, FACEP
Chief Medical Officer
Keck Hospital of **USC**
USC Norris Cancer Hospital
Associate Dean Clinical Affairs,
USC Keck School of Medicine
Chief Clinical Officer, University Clinical Services

Appendix B

IRB Approvals

University of Southern California Institutional Review Board
 3720 S. Flower Street, Suite 325
 Los Angeles, CA 90089
 Telephone: (323) 442-0114
 Fax: (323) 224-8389
 Email: irb@usc.edu

Date: Oct 11, 2022, 02:45pm
 Action Taken: **Approve**
 Principal Investigator: [Melanie Cariker, MSN, RN](#)
 Faculty Advisor: [Ellen Whalen](#)
 Co-Investigator(s):
 Project Title: [HAPI Prevention Algorithm](#)
 Study ID: **UP-22-00648**
 Funding:

The University of Southern California Institutional Review Board (IRB) designee reviewed your iStar application and attachments on 10/11/2022.

Based on the information submitted for review, this study is determined to be exempt from 45 CFR 46 according to §46.104(d) as category (2, 3).

As research which is considered exempt according to §46.104(d), this project is not subject to requirements for continuing review. You are authorized to conduct this research as approved.

If there are significant changes that increase the risk to subjects or if the funding has changed, you must submit an amendment to the IRB for review and approval. For other revisions to the application, use the "Send Message to IRB" link.

The materials submitted and considered for review of this project included:

1. iStar application 9/21/2022
2. Social Behavioral Protocol - revised(0.02), dated 10/6/2022
3. Survey - Views on Pressure Injury Prevention(0.01), dated 9/19/2022
4. Appendix A - Algorithm(0.01), dated 9/19/2022

Principal Investigator Responsibilities:

As the Principal Investigator, you are required to ensure that this research and the actions of all project personnel involved in conducting the study will conform with all federal, state, local and institutional standards and for obtaining all necessary approvals before commencing research. Please be sure that you have satisfied all applicable requirements, for example: conflicts of interest, credentialing, data security, sponsor approval, school district or school approval. IRB approval does not convey approval to commence research in the event that other requirements have not been satisfied.

Information Sheet and Recruitment:

It is the responsibility of the principal investigator to follow the principles of the Belmont Report, which requires all potential participants to be informed of the research study, their rights as a participant, confidentiality of their data, etc. per USC IRB policy.

Consent and recruitment documents are not required to be uploaded to the iStar application for exempt studies. Please utilize the attached Information Sheet For Exempt Research template and Guidance for Recruitment materials. The documents should include the information specific to your study. These documents will not be reviewed by the IRB. It is the responsibility of the researcher to make sure the documents are consistent with the study procedures listed in the application.

NOTE: In the event that this study is audited by the IRB, you are required to provide the Information Sheet and recruitment documents used for this study.

Site Permissions:

As the Principal Investigator, you are responsible for ensuring that your project complies with all federal, state, local and institutional standards. Please check with all participating sites to make sure you have their permission (including IRB/ethics board approval, if applicable) to conduct research prior to beginning your study.

Attachments: [2019-10-31_guidance-for-recruitment-tool-final.pdf](#)
: [Information-Sheet-for-Exempt-Studies-07-27-2019 \(7\).doc](#)

Social-behavioral health-related interventions or health-outcome studies must register with clinicaltrials.gov or other International Community of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) approved registries in order to be published in an ICMJE journal. The ICMJE will not accept studies for publication unless the studies are registered prior to enrollment, despite the fact that these studies are not applicable "clinical trials" as defined by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). For support with registration, go to www.clinicaltrials.gov or contact Jean Chan (jeanbcha@usc.edu, 323-442-2825).

Approved Documents: [view](#)

Important

The principal investigator for this study is responsible for obtaining all necessary approvals before commencing research. Please be sure that you have satisfied applicable requirements, for example conflicts of interest, bio safety, radiation safety, biorepositories, credentialing, data security, sponsor approval, clinicaltrials.gov or school approval. IRB approval does not convey approval to commence research in the event that other requirements have not been satisfied.

This is an auto-generated email. Please do not respond directly to this message using the "reply" address. A response sent in this manner cannot be answered. If you have further questions, please contact iStar Support at (323) 276-2238 or istar@usc.edu.

The contents of this email are confidential and intended for the specified recipients only. If you have received this email in error, please notify istar@usc.edu and delete this message.

From: [Claire Riner](#)
To: [Melanie Cariker](#); [Elizabeth Winokur](#); [Claire Riner](#)
Subject: [External] IRBNet message from Claire Riner 22-39X [1951524-1] Development of a Hospital-Acquired Pressure Injury Prevention Algorithm
Date: Friday, November 4, 2022 5:21:42 PM

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

Message from Claire Riner:

Re: [1951524-1] Development of a Hospital-Acquired Pressure Injury Prevention Algorithm

Melanie,

Thank you for your patience. I read through this IRB application last evening and consulted with Dr. Winokur about the best path forward. Here is the conclusion:

The Cal State LA IRB will accept USC's exemption in lieu of reviewing it again here. Since the project received an exempt determination from USC's IRB (categories 2 & 3) already, then there is no need for Cal State LA to also review it. You are free to begin your project.

Please keep a copy of this message and your exempt determination letter from USC for your records. I will also remind you that even though the project has been determined exempt, it is still considered human subjects research and you will need to follow what is outlined in your protocol with USC.

As for this project on IRBNet, I will administratively withdraw the submission next week. You may receive one or two automated messages, but it does not affect your approval.

If you have questions or concerns, please feel free to contact me by email at IRB@calstatela.edu or by phone at 323-343-3792.

Best Regards,
Claire Riner, MPA, CIP

Appendix C

Use of the PARIHS Framework: Permission Letters

From: Brendan McCormack <brendan.mccormack@sydney.edu.au>
Sent: Monday, February 20, 2023 3:19 AM
To: Cariker, Melanie <melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu>; alison.kitson@flinders.edu.au
<alison.kitson@flinders.edu.au>; gillian.harvey@flinders.edu.au <gillian.harvey@flinders.edu.au>
Subject: [External] Re: PARIHS framework permission

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

Dear Melanie

Thanks for your email. It is fine from my perspective for you to include the PARIHS Framework in your paper/poster with the appropriate referencing of the figure. Good luck with your work. I am sure Gill and Alison will respond accordingly.

Best Regards

BRENDAN

Brendan McCormack, Head of School & Dean | *The Susan Wakil Professor of Nursing*

Susan Wakil School of Nursing and Midwifery | Sydney Nursing School

Faculty of Medicine and Health

President Omega Xi Chapter Sigma Global

Pronouns: he/him ([what's this?](#))

THE UNIVERSITY OF SYDNEY

Level 8 East, D18 Susan Wakil Health Building, Camperdown | Gadigal | NSW | 2050

E brendan.mccormack@sydney.edu.au | **W** sydney.edu.au/nursing | **T** +61403697898 |

The Susan Wakil School of Nursing and Midwifery acknowledges the traditional custodians upon whose ancestral lands the University of Sydney campuses stand and pay our respects to Elders both past, present and emerging.

From: Gillian Harvey <gillian.harvey@flinders.edu.au>
Sent: Monday, February 20, 2023 2:17 PM
To: Cariker, Melanie <melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu>; Brendan McCormack

<brendan.mccormack@sydney.edu.au>; Alison Kitson <alison.kitson@flinders.edu.au>

Subject: [External] RE: PARIHS framework permission

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

All good with me as well Melanie. Good luck with your doctoral project.

Best wishes

Gill

Professor Gillian Harvey

PhD BNurs

Matthew Flinders Professor

Deputy Director – Knowledge Translation, Caring Futures Institute

Co-Director, Aged Care Partnering Program, Aged Care Research and

Industry Innovation Australia (ARIIA)

College of Nursing and Health Sciences

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www.flinders.edu.au/people/gillian.harvey

**Flinders
University**

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5042

GPO Box 2100 Adelaide SA

5001

Flinders University acknowledges the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the lands on which its campuses are located, these are the Traditional Lands of the Arrernte, Dagoman, First Nations of the South-East, First Peoples of the River Murray & Mallee region, Jawoyn, Kurna, Larrakia, Ngadjuri, Ngarrindjeri, Ramindjeri, Warumungu, Wardaman and Yolngu people. We honour their Elders past, present and emerging.

CRICOS Provider Number: 00114A This email and any attachments may be confidential. If you are not the intended recipient, please inform the sender by reply email and delete all copies of this message.

Please consider the environment before printing this email.

From: Alison Kitson <alison.kitson@flinders.edu.au>

Sent: Monday, February 20, 2023 4:00 PM

To: Gillian Harvey <gillian.harvey@flinders.edu.au>; Cariker, Melanie

<melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu>; Brendan McCormack <brendan.mccormack@sydney.edu.au>
Subject: [External] Re: PARIHS framework permission

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

And me too!

Alison

Alison Kitson (Professor)
RN, BSc(Hons), DPhil, FRCN, FAAN, FAHMS
Matthew Flinders Distinguished Professor
Vice President and Executive Dean
College of Nursing and Health Sciences
alison.kitson@flinders.edu.au +61 8 8201 3492
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GPO Box 2100 Adelaide SA 5001

Flinders University acknowledges the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the lands on which its campuses are located, these are the Traditional Lands of the Arrernte, Dagoman, First Nations of the South-East, First Peoples of the River Murray & Mallee region, Jawoyn, Kaurna, Larrakia, Ngadjuri, Ngarrindjeri, Ramindjeri, Warumungu, Wardaman and Yolngu people. We honour their Elders past, present and emerging.

CRICOS Provider Number: 00114A This email and any attachments may be confidential. If you are not the intended recipient, please inform the sender by reply email and delete all copies of this message.

Please consider the environment before printing this email.

Appendix D

Figure 1: PARIHS Framework

Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) Framework

Rycroft-Malone, 2004

Appendix E

Figure 2: Integration of the PARIHS Framework

Kitson et al., 2008 & Rycroft- Malone, 2004

Note: SI = Successful Implementation, E = evidence, F = facilitation, C = context

Appendix F

Informational Cover Letter

ANALYZING THE VIEWS ON PRESSURE INJURY PREVENTION AMONG NURSES IN THE MEDICAL INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a project conducted by Melanie Cariker, MSN, RN, a doctoral nursing student at California State University DNP Consortium and Elizabeth Winokur PhD, RN, an associate professor, at California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA). In this project, we hope to learn more about the nurses' views on pressure injury prevention at Keck Hospital of USC. You were invited to participate in this project because you met all the inclusion criteria. We hope to gather the information that will contribute to patient care using evidence-based practices. Furthermore, this will form the basis for the development of an educational strategy for pressure injury prevention and management.

An email invitation to participate in the project with a hyperlink to the survey will be sent to your work email which was provided by the unit manager. Individuals who agree to participate in the project will access the survey through the hyperlink created from the online software program called Qualtrics. You will be asked to participate in a 10-minute-long survey. The first portion of the survey is an 11-item 5-point Likert scale survey to learn your views on pressure injury prevention at Keck Hospital of USC. Participants can skip any questions they do not wish to answer. The survey will be available to you for up to two weeks. No compensation will be included for your participation, and lack of participation will neither be a work requirement nor affect your performance evaluation with Keck Hospital of USC.

This project has no medical risks, as you will not be exposed to any medical treatments. You will only be providing information regarding your perceptions.

Reports resulting from this project will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this project will remain confidential. If you choose to participate, your confidentiality will be protected. The project has minimal risk for loss of confidentiality as no personal contact or identifying information (ex. name, number, email, signature, etc.) is asked or required at any point during the start and completion of your participation in the project. The online survey is being disseminated using Qualtrics, which has the capability of collecting and storing of the participant's data; however, no personal user information will be collected, other than the data collected from survey responses. Furthermore, the de-identified data from the completed surveys will only be viewed and accessed by project investigators. All data will be stored in a secured, password-enabled computer. The data will be kept and stored for three years following the completion of the project and destroyed thereafter.

It is not anticipated that there are unforeseeable risks to participants. Participation in the project will occur at no financial cost and will take no more than 10 minutes of your time. There will be no consequences for participants that withdraw from the project and a participant can withdraw at any time. Furthermore, the decision to participate or not in this project will have no effect on your performance evaluation with Keck Hospital of USC.

If you have any questions about this project at any time, please call/text Melanie Cariker at (626) 213-9244 or email her at melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu. The overseeing faculty and committee chair of this project is Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, who can also be contacted for questions or concerns at (714)-402-4270 or email her at ewinoku2@calstatela.edu.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

Appendix G

Qualtrics Survey

You are invited to take part in a project conducted by Melanie Cariker, MSN, RN, a doctoral nursing student at California State University DNP Consortium and Elizabeth Winokur PhD, RN, an associate professor, at California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA). In this project, we hope to learn more about the nurses' views on pressure injury prevention at Keck Hospital of USC. You are receiving this survey because you meet the following inclusion criteria to participate in the proposed project: 1. Registered Nurse (RN) 2. Must currently be working part-time or full-time at Keck Hospital's Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU). Participation in the survey will occur at no financial cost and will take no more than 10 minutes of your time. You may skip any questions that you do not wish to answer. You will not be asked to provide any personal contact or identifying information such as your name, phone number, or email. No compensation will be included for your participation, and lack of participation will neither be a work requirement nor affect your performance evaluation with Keck Hospital of USC. All information gathered in this project will remain confidential. If you choose to participate, your confidentiality will be protected. If you have any questions about this project at any time, please call/text Melanie Cariker at (626) 213-9244 or email her at melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu The overseeing faculty and committee chair of this project is Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, who can also be contacted for questions or concerns at (714)-402-4270 or email her at ewinoku2@calstatela.edu.

Mobile View

A screenshot of a mobile survey interface. The top of the screen shows the time 12:29, signal strength, and battery level. The main content area contains the following text and questions:

Please answer how much you agree or disagree with the statements below:

1. All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries. Strongly agree, Somewhat agree, Neither agree nor disagree, Somewhat disagree, Strongly disagree. A chevron icon is on the right.
2. Pressure injury prevention is time-consuming for me to carry out. A chevron icon is on the right.
3. In my opinion, patients tend not to get as many pressure injuries nowadays. A chevron icon is on the right.
4. I do not need to concern myself with pressure injury prevention in my practice. A chevron icon is on the right.
5. Pressure injury treatment is a greater priority than pressure injury prevention. A chevron icon is on the right.

Online View

Please answer how much you agree or disagree with the statements below:

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
1. All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Pressure injury prevention is time-consuming for me to carry out.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. In my opinion, patients tend not to get as many pressure injuries nowadays.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. I do not need to concern myself with pressure injury prevention in my practice.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Pressure injury treatment is a greater priority than pressure injury prevention.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Continuous assessment of patients will give an accurate account of their pressure injury risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Most pressure injuries can be avoided.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. I am less interested in pressure injury prevention than other aspects of care.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. My clinical judgment is better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. In comparison with other areas of care, pressure injury prevention is a low priority for me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11. Pressure injury risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay in hospital.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Appendix H

Email Invitation: Pre-Intervention Survey

Dear MICU RN,

You are receiving this email because you meet the following inclusion criteria to participate in the proposed study:

1. Registered Nurse (RN)
2. Must currently be working part-time or full-time at Keck Hospital's 5 ICU Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU)

If you wish to participate in the following research study, please click on the hyperlink to the online survey/questionnaire down below. Upon clicking on the hyperlink to the online survey/questionnaire, you will be prompted to the informational cover sheet, which will provide more instructions and information on the study's background, purpose, risks, and benefits. Proceeding from the informational cover sheet will take participants to the 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. The survey should take approximately 10 minutes to complete. You may skip any questions that you do not wish to answer. At **no point** during the survey will you be asked to provide any personal contact or identifying information (name, number, email, etc.) to protect your confidentiality.

Hyperlink to survey/questionnaire:

https://usc.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_a60dY6GGewflKvQ

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call/text **Melanie Cariker** at (626)213-9244 or email her at melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu. The overseeing faculty and committee chair of this project, **Dr. Elizabeth Winokur**, can also be contacted for questions or concerns at (714) 402-4270 or email her at ewinoku2@calstatela.edu.

With Gratitude,

Melanie Cariker, MSN-Ed, RN, CPHQ
DNP Student, Cohort 10
Southern California Consortium
California State University

Appendix I

Email Invitation: Post-Intervention Survey

Dear MICU RN,

You are receiving this post-intervention survey email because you meet the following inclusion criteria to participate in the proposed study:

1. Registered Nurse (RN)
2. Must currently be working part-time or full-time at Keck Hospital's 5 ICU Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU)

If you wish to participate in the following research study, please click on the hyperlink to the online survey/questionnaire down below. Upon clicking on the hyperlink to the online survey/questionnaire, you will be prompted to the informational cover sheet, which will provide more instructions and information on the study's background, purpose, risks, and benefits. Proceeding from the informational cover sheet will take participants to the 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. The survey should take approximately 10 minutes to complete. You may skip any questions that you do not wish to answer. At **no point** during the survey will you be asked to provide any personal contact or identifying information (name, number, email, etc.) to protect your confidentiality.

Hyperlink to survey/questionnaire:

https://usc.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_86Aq6CH4e3HcX3w

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call/text **Melanie Cariker** at (626)213-9244 or email her at melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu. The overseeing faculty and committee chair of this project, **Dr. Elizabeth Winokur**, can also be contacted for questions or concerns at (714) 402-4270 or email her at ewinoku2@calstatela.edu.

With Gratitude,

Melanie Cariker, MSN-Ed, RN, CPHQ
DNP Student, Cohort 10
Southern California Consortium
California State University

Appendix J

HAPI Prevention Algorithm

Hospital-Acquired Pressure Injury (HAPI) Prevention Algorithm

If you have any questions about this algorithm at any time, please call/text Melanie Cariker at (626) 213-9244 or email her at melaniecariker@csu.fullerton.edu. The overseeing faculty and committee chair of this project, Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, can also be contacted for questions or concerns at (714)-402-4270 or email her at ewinoku2@calstatela.edu.

Appendix K

Pre-Intervention Survey Results

Table 1

Pre-Intervention Survey Responses on Pressure Injury Prevention

Survey Questions	Strongly Disagree % (n)	Somewhat Disagree % (n)	Neither Agree or Disagree % (n)	Somewhat Agree % (n)	Strongly Agree % (n)
1. All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries.	12% (2)	0% (0)	6% (1)	29% (5)	53% (9)
2. Pressure injury prevention is time-consuming for me to carry out.	41% (7)	6% (1)	12% (2)	24% (4)	18% (3)
3. In my opinion, patients tend not to get as many pressure injuries nowadays.	47% (8)	6% (1)	24% (4)	6% (1)	18% (3)
4. I do not need to concern myself with pressure injury prevention in my practice.	71% (12)	12% (2)	0% (0)	0% (0)	18% (3)
5. Pressure injury treatment is a greater priority than pressure injury prevention.	29% (5)	35% (6)	18% (3)	0% (0)	18% (3)
6. Continuous assessment of patients will give an accurate account of their pressure injury risk.	18% (3)	0% (0)	6% (1)	6% (1)	71% (12)
7. Most pressure injuries can be avoided.	18% (3)	6% (1)	6% (1)	35% (6)	35% (6)
8. I am less interested in pressure injury prevention than other aspects of care.	41% (7)	24% (4)	18% (3)	0% (0)	18% (3)
9. My clinical judgment is better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to me.	24% (4)	6% (1)	47% (8)	6% (1)	18% (3)
10. In comparison with other areas of care, pressure injury prevention is a low priority for me.	53% (9)	18% (3)	12% (2)	0% (0)	18% (3)
11. Pressure injury risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay in hospital.	12% (2)	0% (0)	6% (1)	12% (2)	71% (12)

Note: n=17

Appendix L

Post-Intervention Survey Results

Table 2

Post-Intervention Survey Responses on Pressure Injury Prevention

Survey Questions	Strongly Disagree % (n)	Somewhat Disagree % (n)	Neither Agree or Disagree % (n)	Somewhat Agree % (n)	Strongly Agree % (n)
1. All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries.	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	29% (5)	71% (12)
2. Pressure injury prevention is time-consuming for me to carry out.	53% (9)	12% (2)	6% (1)	29% (5)	0% (0)
3. In my opinion, patients tend not to get as many pressure injuries nowadays.	65% (11)	12% (2)	18% (3)	6% (1)	0% (0)
4. I do not need to concern myself with pressure injury prevention in my practice.	100%(17)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)
5. Pressure injury treatment is a greater priority than pressure injury prevention.	71% (12)	18% (3)	6% (1)	0% (0)	0% (1)
6. Continuous assessment of patients will give an accurate account of their pressure injury risk.	6% (1)	0% (0)	0% (0)	6% (1)	0% (15)
7. Most pressure injuries can be avoided.	0% (0)	12% (2)	24% (4)	12% (2)	6% (9)
8. I am less interested in pressure injury prevention than other aspects of care.	65% (11)	0% (0)	35% (6)	0% (0)	0% (0)
9. My clinical judgment is better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to me.	59% (10)	24% (4)	12% (2)	6% (1)	0% (0)
10. In comparison with other areas of care, pressure injury prevention is a low priority for me.	65% (11)	29% (5)	6% (1)	0% (0)	0% (0)
11. Pressure injury risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay in hospital.	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	0% (0)	100% (17)

Note: n=17; Bolded items indicated statistical significance.

Appendix M

t-Test Results

Table 3

t-Test Results

Survey Questions	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>
1. All patients are at potential risk of developing pressure injuries.	-2.12	.048
2. Pressure injury prevention is time-consuming for me to carry out.	1.187	.245
3. In my opinion, patients tend not to get as many pressure injuries nowadays.	1.69	.103
4. I do not need to concern myself with pressure injury prevention in my practice.	.395	.696
5. Pressure injury treatment is a greater priority than pressure injury prevention.	1.69	.102
6. Continuous assessment of patients will give an accurate account of their pressure injury risk.	-1.31	.201
7. Most pressure injuries can be avoided.	-.643	.524
8. I am less interested in pressure injury prevention than other aspects of care.	1.36	.186
9. My clinical judgment is better than any pressure injury risk assessment tool available to me.	2.95	.006
10. In comparison with other areas of care, pressure injury prevention is a low priority for me.	1.76	.706
11. Pressure injury risk assessment should be regularly carried out on all patients during their stay in hospital.	-2.14	.040

Note: $n=17$; Bolded items indicated statistical significance.